

ASSESSMENT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT ON AGRICULTURE USING REMOTE SENSING AND GIS. CASE STUDY: NYAGATARE DISTRICT

Author: DUSHIMIRIMANA Philbert

ABSTRACT

This study assesses the impact of climate change on agriculture in Nyagatare District, Rwanda, by analyzing land use/land cover (LULC) changes from 2016 to 2024 using Remote Sensing and GIS techniques. The findings show significant land cover transformations, with a shift from agricultural and forested areas to built-up and bare lands. In 2016, agriculture dominated the landscape, covering 44.52%, but by 2024, agricultural land decreased, and built-up areas expanded to 42.17%. Key transitions include the conversion of agricultural land to urban areas (17,947.23 ha), forests to bare land (26,653.17 ha), and wetlands to urban zones (33,126.69 ha), reflecting urban expansion, land degradation, and deforestation driven by population growth

and economic activities. Temperature differences across the district (22°C–24°C in the east, 18°C–20°C in the west) impact evaporation, irrigation needs, and livestock farming, while varying rainfall patterns (800-1000 mm in the north and central regions, 1200-1600 mm in the south) affect water availability. To mitigate the effects of climate change, the study proposes sustainable agricultural practices, water-efficient irrigation, agroforestry, improved water management, renewable energy investments, and reforestation. These strategies aim to reduce climate change impacts, enhance food security, and promote sustainable agriculture in Nyagatare.

Keywords: *Climate, Agriculture, Climate change and remote sensing.*

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	1
LIST OF TABLES	iii
LIST OF FIGURES	iv
LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ACRONYMS	v
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2. Problem Statement	3
1.3. Objectives.....	4
1.3.1. General objective	4
1.3.2. Specific objectives	4
1.4. Project research question.....	4
1.5. Interest of the study	4
1.5.1. Personnel Interests.....	5
1.5.2. Academic and scientific interest.....	5
1.5.3. Social interest	5
1.6. Organization of the study	5
1.7. Expected Outputs	6
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	7
2.1 Introduction	7
2.2 Definitions of concept terms	8
2.2.1 Climate	8
2.2.1 Agriculture	8
2.2.2 Climate change	8
2.2.3 Remote sensing	9
2.2.4. Relationship between climate change and Agriculture	9
2.3 Types of Climate	10
2.4. Role of weather satellites	11

2.5. Impact of climate change	12
2.6. Causes of Global Climate Change.....	13
2.7. Effects of Climate Change on Crop Production.....	14
2.8. Relationship between Crop Production and Climate Change	15
2.9. Measure to mitigate impact of climate change on agriculture	16
2.10. Introduction to GIS.....	19
2.10.1. Components of GIS	19
CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	21
3.1. Introduction	21
3.2: DESCRIPTION OF STUDY AREA	21
3.3. Data Collection.....	22
3.4. Data processing	23
3.4.1. Image Pre-Processing	23
3.4.2. Image processing	23
2. Accuracy assessment	24
3. Change detection	24
3.5. Flow Chart of Methodology	26
CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	27
4.1. Results	27
4.2. Land use/land cover of the Nyagatare district in 2016.....	27
4.3. Land use/land cover of the study area in 2024.	30
4.5. Change Detection Map of Nyagatare District 2016-2024.....	32
4.6. Impact of Changing Rainfall Patterns on Agricultural Productivity in Nyagatare District	36
4.7. Climate change mitigation measures.....	38
CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	41
5.1 Conclusions	41
5.2. Recommendations	42
References	43

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4. 1: Class and percentage of LULC 2016.....	29
Table 4. 2: Class and percentage of LULC 2024.....	31
Table 4. 3: Classes of change detection from 2016 to 2024	34

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2. 1: Climate zones appear on a globe.....	11
Figure 2. 2: Relationship between Crop Production and Climate Change	16
Figure 3. 1: Study area map	22
Figure 3. 2: Methodology flow chart	26
Figure 4. 1: LULC Map of Nyagatare district 2016	28
Figure 4. 2: Bar chart of LULC 2016	29
Figure 4. 3: : LULC Map of Nyagatare district 2024	30
Figure 4. 4: Bar chart of LULC 2024	31
Figure 4. 5: Change detection map of Nyagatare district 2016-2024.....	33
Figure 4. 6: Bar chart change detection 2016 – 2024	34
Figure 4. 7: Map showing rainfall of Nyagatare district.....	37
Figure 4. 8: Map showing temperature of Nyagatare district	38

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ACRONYMS

ArcGIS: Geographic Information System software by Esri

EASAC: European Academies' Science Advisory Council

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization

GHG: Greenhouse Gas

GIS: Geographic Information System

GLADA: Global Assessment of Land Degradation and Improvement

GPS: Global Positioning System

LUCF: Land Use Change and Forestry

LULC: Land Use and Land Cover

Ms Excel: Microsoft Excel

RS: Remote Sensing

Tiff: Tagged Image File Format

UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme

USD: United States Dollar

USGS: United States Geological Survey

WFP: World Food Programme

WHO: World Health Organization

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Climate change is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth's local, regional and global climates[1]. Climate change is resulting into a very high rate of land degradation causing enhanced desertification and nutrient deficient soils. The menace of land degradation is increasing by the day and has been characterized as a major global threat. According to Global Assessment of Land Degradation and Improvement (GLADA) a quarter of land area around the globe can now be marked as degraded. Land degradation is supposed to influence lives of 1.5 billion people and 15 billion tons of fertile soil is lost every year due to anthropogenic activities and climate change. Land degradation is resulting in mass migrations and as per a report published by United Nations Environment Programme in 2017, 500 million hectares of farmland has been abandoned due to drought and desertification resulting in major social and environmental constraints [2]. Extreme drought conditions, frequently occurring due to climate change, exacerbate the productivity of crops by causing nutrient immobilization and salt accumulation in soils making them dry, unhealthy, saline and finally infertile. Such barren lands become non-arable with course of time and are eventually abandoned by farmers leading to economic losses and social issues. Projected climate variations are not limited to only increase in drought conditions. Climate change has also resulted in increased and sporadic incidences of floods in last few years.

Report by European Academies' Science Advisory Council (EASAC) suggests that extreme events including floods have increased by 50% in last 10 years and are now occurring at rate of four times higher than in comparison to 20 years back. Heavy floods in Kerala, India, in 2018 are a glaring example to showcase this. These floods have resulted in washout of top soil and nutrients from the soil, resulting in low productivity for several years to come, unless and until corrective and pro-active remediation strategies are not worked upon. Rise in sea levels or prevalence of heavy rainfall could result in decline of agricultural lands in coastal regions. This has also resulted in salinity of soils in coastal regions leading to stresses in crops such as decreased respiration, photosynthesis and transpiration, ultimately jeopardizing food availability and security in such regions [3]. Climate change threatens people with increased flooding, extreme heat, increased food and water scarcity, more disease, and economic loss. Human migration and conflict can also be a result. The World Health Organization calls climate change one of the

biggest threats to global health in the 21st century. Societies and ecosystems will experience more severe risks without action to limit warming. Adapting to climate change through efforts like flood control measures or drought-resistant crops partially reduces climate change risks, although some limits to adaptation have already been reached. Poorer communities are responsible for a small share of global emissions, yet have the least ability to adapt and are most vulnerable to climate change. Examples of some effects of climate change: Wildfire intensified by heat and drought, bleaching of corals occurring more often due to marine heatwaves, and worsening droughts compromising water supplies [4].

Many climate change impacts have been observed in the first decades of the 21st century, with 2024 the warmest on record at +1.60 °C (2.88 °F) since regular tracking began in 1850. Additional warming will increase these impacts and can trigger tipping points, such as melting all of the Greenland ice sheet. Under the 2015 Paris Agreement, nations collectively agreed to keep warming "well under 2 °C". However, with pledges made under the Agreement, global warming would still reach about 2.8 °C (5.0 °F) by the end of the century. Limiting warming to 1.5 °C would require halving emissions by 2030 and achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 [5].

Climate change is one of the most defining concerns of today's world and has greatly reshaped or in process of altering earth's ecosystems. Although climate change has been a constant process on earth, but in recent times, approximately last 100 years or so, the pace of this variation has increased manifolds. Due to the anthropogenic activities the average temperature has risen by 0.9 °C since nineteenth century, mainly due to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the atmosphere. As per estimates this rise is expected to be 1.5 °C by 2050 or may be even more, the way deforestation is occurring, GHG emission is increasing and soil, water bodies and air are being polluted [6]. The unprecedented hike in temperature has resulted in increased events of droughts, floods, irregular patterns of precipitation, heat waves and other extreme happenings throughout the globe. As per the annual report of Weather, Climate and Catastrophe Insight, natural disasters alone have caused economic losses in tune of USD 225 billion across the world in 2018 and since 2016 the losses due to natural calamities have crossed USD 200 billion per year. About 95% of these losses are attributed to weather related incidences, of which cyclones, floods and droughts are the key players and are directly related to climate change. Altogether, the impact of climate change is very comprehensive but its far reaching effects are now clearly visible on agricultural

sector, on which relies the food production and economy of the world [7]. It is also worth noting that world population is expected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050 which would magnify the pressure on agricultural lands to meet the growing food demands already affected by the impact of climate change. As climate change and agriculture have inextricable links, abrupt changes in climatic conditions at such a rapid pace has threatened the food security at global scale. World Food Programme (WFP) report of 2018 revealed that increase in crop yield per hectare is significantly slower as compared to rates of rising population. As per Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) data published in 2016, if the current situation of GHG emissions and climate change continue then by the year 2100 there will be decline in the production of major cereal crops (20–45% in maize yields, 5–50% in wheat and 20–30% in rice). Hence if the trends continue, in very near future crop losses may increase at an unprecedented rate which will substantially contribute to reduced production, spiked food prices, and it will become difficult to cope up with rising needs of growing population. due to drought and desertification resulting in major social and environmental constraints. Extreme drought conditions, frequently occurring due to climate change, exacerbate the productivity of crops by causing nutrient immobilization and salt accumulation in soils making them dry, unhealthy, saline and finally infertile [8].

1.2. Problem Statement

Climate change is a serious challenge for agriculture in Rwanda as whole world. This district has a semi-arid climate, and most farmers depend on rain-fed agriculture. However, in recent years, rainfall has become unpredictable, droughts have become more frequent, and temperatures have increased. These changes are making farming more difficult and reducing food production. One major problem is irregular rainfall patterns. Sometimes, farmers receive too much rain in a short period, causing floods and soil erosion, which wash away fertile soil. Other times, long dry periods occur, leading to water shortages and poor crop growth. This has resulted in declining crop yields, making it harder for farmers to produce enough food. Another issue is the loss of soil fertility due to climate change. As temperatures rise, soil moisture decreases, making the land less productive. In addition, the increased presence of pests and plant diseases caused by warmer temperatures damages crops and reduces harvests. As food production declines and costs rise, food security is at risk, and farmers are struggling to earn a living. If these challenges are not addressed, Nyagatare's agricultural sector will continue to suffer, putting pressure on the economy

and local communities. To solve these problems, there is a need for a detailed assessment of how climate change is affecting agriculture in Nyagatare. Understanding these impacts will help in developing better farming practices, water management strategies, and policies to support farmers and ensure sustainable food production in the district.

1.3. Objectives

1.3.1. General objective

The primary objective of this study is to assess impact of climate change on agriculture in Nyagatare district using remote sensing and GIS.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

1. To assess the land use/land cover of the study area in 2016 and 2024.
2. To assess land cover changes due to climate change in Nyagatare, using Landsat images from 2016 and 2024.
3. To assess the impact of changing rainfall patterns on agricultural productivity in Nyagatare District.
4. To propose climate change mitigation measures.

1.4. Project research question

1. what extent has land use/land cover in Nyagatare District changed between 2016 and 2024?
2. What specific changes in land cover have occurred in Nyagatare District between 2016 and 2024, and how can these changes be attributed to climate variability and agricultural activities?
3. How can the analysis of land use/land cover changes in Nyagatare District from 2016 to 2024 inform the development of effective climate change mitigation measures for the region?
4. How have changing rainfall patterns in Nyagatare District between 2016 and 2024 influenced agricultural productivity?

1.5. Interest of the study

This study will provide the researcher with valuable experience in using remote sensing and GIS software to assess impact of climate change on agriculture in Nyagatare district. It will further give the researcher greater understanding of the importance of research and methods that can be used

to conduct such researcher and its successful completion will make researcher be qualified for underground degree in land survey. The study will also help policymakers and environmental authorities to make informed decisions regarding land use, sustainable farming practices, and climate adaptation strategies. Additionally, the results of this study will help to identify areas of concern that require further research and intervention.

1.5.1. Personnel Interests

As an environmental enthusiast with a focus on sustainable resource management, I am deeply interested in using geospatial techniques such as remote sensing and GIS to analyze the impact of climate change on agriculture. This study will provide me with valuable skills and experience in these methods, further strengthening my commitment to understanding and addressing the challenges posed by climate change. I am eager to explore innovative approaches to mitigate these impacts and contribute to sustainable agricultural practices that support environmental conservation for future generations.

1.5.2. Academic and scientific interest

This study will serve as a valuable reference for researchers and students interested in analyzing the impact of climate change on agriculture using geospatial techniques, particularly within the Department of Civil engineering, option of Bachelor of Technology in Geomatics. Its findings will contribute to future academic endeavors in various fields.

1.5.3. Social interest

The society is composed of various individuals, mainly citizens and officers. This study will awake the citizens to know different role of their climate especially those who live in the study area where this research will be conducted. This also will help officers to make assessment of the climate change and decision making in Nyagatare.

1.6. Organization of the study

This study is organized in following five chapters:

1. The first chapter will deal with the background information to the study, the definition of the research problem, objectives and their corresponding research questions, interest of the topic, scope and limitation of the study.

2. In the second chapter some definitions and literature review related to the impact assessment of climate change on agriculture.
3. Chapter will three explain the methodology used to conduct this research where source of data used, equipment used in collection of data, description of the study area of this research are shown and discussed.
4. Chapter four will show the analysis and interpretation of the results.
5. Finally, Chapter five, which closes the report, will provides a summary to the content in the report and gives recommendations and conclusion for future works.

1.7. Expected Outputs

This study aims to assess land use and land cover changes in Nyagatare District between 2016 and 2024, focusing on the impact of climate change on agriculture, particularly vegetation health and crop yields. The expected outputs include a detailed analysis of land use and land cover in both years, using Landsat images to identify land cover changes linked to climate change. Additionally, the study will evaluate how shifting rainfall patterns affect agricultural productivity in the district and propose climate change mitigation measures. These will include recommendations for climate-smart agricultural practices and sustainable land management to enhance agricultural resilience in Nyagatare

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Climate change is significantly affecting Rwanda's agriculture, a sector that supports the majority of the population. Rising temperatures, irregular rainfall, prolonged droughts, and frequent floods disrupt farming activities, reducing crop yields and livestock productivity. Staple crops such as maize, beans, and bananas are particularly vulnerable to erratic weather patterns, leading to food insecurity and economic instability for smallholder farmers. Soil erosion, worsened by heavy rains, depletes soil fertility, while prolonged dry spells limit water availability for irrigation. Additionally, climate change has led to increased pest and disease outbreaks, further threatening agricultural productivity [9]. Livestock farming is also affected by heat stress, reduced pasture availability, and water shortages.

Agriculture contributes to development as an economic activity, as a livelihood, and as a provider of environmental services, making the sector a unique instrument for growth and poverty reduction. In Rwanda, over 80% of employment is based in rural areas. Agriculture is the main sector making up 32% of GDP. Agriculture in Rwanda faces multiple challenges. Land is scarce and population densities high, which means the median land size is approximately 0.3 ha per household. Smallholder farmers dominate production, with complex extension needs. The country is also landlocked, which creates higher energy and transport costs than regional neighbors. Rwanda's unique topography means that farm activity depends on a diverse range of geographical landscapes and micro-climates. The climate variability of Rwanda is one of the most significant factors influencing year to year crop production. Even in high-technology agricultural areas that factor remains one of the most important. In recent years, more and more attention has been paid to the risks associated with climate change, and the increase uncertainty with respect to food production [10].

Rwanda is located in a tropical temperate climate due to its high altitude. The average annual temperature ranges between 16°C and 20°C, without significant variations. Rainfall is abundant although it has some irregularities. Winds are generally around 1-3 m/s. In the high regions of the Congo-Nile ridge, average temperatures ranges between 15°C and 17°C and the rainfall is abundant. The volcanic region has much lower temperatures that can go below 0°C in some places. In areas with intermediary altitude, average temperatures vary between 19°C and

21°C and the average rainfall is around 1000 mm/year. Rainfall is less irregular, and sometimes causes periods of drought. In the lowlands (East and Southeast), temperatures are higher and the extreme can go beyond 30°C in February and July-August [11].

2.2 Definitions of concept terms

2.2.1 Climate

Climate is the general weather over a long period. This can include rainfall, temperature, snow or any other weather condition. We usually define a region's climate over a period of 30 years. Otherwise Climate is the general weather over a long period. This can include rainfall, temperature, snow or any other weather condition. We usually define a region's climate over a period of 30 years. Otherwise, Climate refers to the long-term patterns and averages of weather conditions in a particular region over an extended period, typically 30 years or more. It includes factors such as temperature, humidity, precipitation, wind patterns, and atmospheric pressure. Climate differs from weather, which describes short-term atmospheric conditions. Different regions have distinct climates, such as tropical, temperate, arid, and polar, influenced by latitude, altitude, ocean currents, and other environmental factors [12].

2.2.1 Agriculture

Agriculture is the practice of growing crops and raising animals for food, fiber, and other products. It involves activities like planting, cultivating, and harvesting crops, as well as caring for animals. Agriculture is the practice of cultivating plants and raising animals for food, fiber, medicinal plants, and other products used to sustain and enhance human life. It includes activities such as farming, livestock breeding, aquaculture, forestry, and agro-processing. Agriculture is essential for food security, economic development, and rural livelihoods, and it plays a crucial role in global trade and environmental sustainability [13].

2.2.2 Climate change

Climate change is the significant variation of average weather conditions becoming, for example, warmer, wetter, or drier-over several decades or longer. It is the longer-term trend that differentiates climate change from natural weather variability. Otherwise, Climate Change refers to long-term shifts in temperature, precipitation, wind patterns, and other elements of the Earth's

climate system. It is primarily driven by human activities, such as burning fossil fuels, deforestation, and industrial emissions, which increase greenhouse gases (CO₂, methane) in the atmosphere. These changes result in rising global temperatures, extreme weather events, sea level rise, and disruptions to ecosystems, agriculture, and water resources. Climate change poses significant challenges to economies, biodiversity, and human livelihoods, requiring urgent mitigation and adaptation efforts [14].

2.2.3 Remote sensing

Remote sensing refers to the process of collecting data about objects or areas from a distance, typically using satellite or aerial imagery. It involves capturing reflected or emitted radiation from the Earth's surface to gather information about land, water, and vegetation. This technology helps in monitoring environmental changes, urban growth, and natural resources. Sensors on satellites or drones detect various wavelengths, such as visible light, infrared, and radar. Remote sensing is widely used in fields like agriculture, forestry, urban planning, and disaster management. It provides valuable insights without direct contact, making it a non-invasive and efficient tool [15].

2.2.4. Relationship between climate change and Agriculture

Climate change is a major global challenge, characterized by rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall patterns, and an increase in extreme weather events such as droughts, floods, and storms. These changes significantly impact natural ecosystems, human societies, and economic activities. Agriculture, which provides food, employment, and economic stability, is highly vulnerable to climate change. Changes in temperature and precipitation directly affect crop growth, soil fertility, and water availability. Extreme weather events can destroy harvests, reduce livestock productivity, and increase the spread of pests and diseases. In many regions, declining agricultural productivity threatens food security and the livelihoods of millions, particularly in developing countries that rely heavily on farming [16].

2.3 Types of Climate

Climate is the average weather conditions in a place over a long period of time 30 years or more. And as you probably already know, there are lots of different types of climates on Earth. For example, hot regions are normally closest to the equator [17]. The climate is hotter there because the Sun's light is most directly overhead at the equator. And the North and South Poles are cold because the Sun's light and heat are least direct there. There are approximately five main climate types on Earth:

- ✚ Tropical
- ✚ Dry
- ✚ Temperate
- ✚ Continental
- ✚ Polar [18].

Today, climate scientists split the Earth into approximately five main types of climates. They are:

- ✚ **A: Tropical.** In this hot and humid zone, the average temperatures are greater than 64°F (18°C) year-round and there is more than 59 inches of precipitation each year.
- ✚ **B: Dry.** These climate zones are so dry because moisture is rapidly evaporated from the air and there is very little precipitation.
- ✚ **C: Temperate.** In this zone, there are typically warm and humid summers with thunderstorms and mild winters.
- D. Continental.** These regions have warm to cool summers and very cold winters. In the winter, this zone can experience snowstorms, strong winds, and very cold temperatures sometimes falling below -22°F (-30°C).
- E: Polar.** In the polar climate zones, it's extremely cold. Even in summer, the temperatures here never go higher than 50°F (10°C) [12].

Figure 2. 1: Climate zones appear on a globe [19].

2.4. Role of weather satellites

Weather satellites mostly help with tracking conditions that are happening right now and forecasting weather in the near future. However, they also collect information that helps us monitor a region's climate over time. For example, satellites in the GOES-R series—short for Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite-R- can monitor the sea surface temperature and the Gulf Stream, a powerful current in the Atlantic Ocean. Both of these things can influence a region's climate. In addition, the temperature of the land becomes cooler at night, and there are changes in the amount of clouds. The GOES-R series satellites monitor cloudiness and land surface temperature information that helps scientists to understand how the differences between day and night can affect a region's climate [20]. Satellites in the Joint Polar Satellite System (JPSS) can

also provide information on differences between day and night. For example, JPSS orbits Earth twice a day in what's called an afternoon orbit. As the satellite orbits from North Pole to South Pole, it captures observations in the afternoon on one side of Earth and observations of the early morning on the other side of the planet. While JPSS orbits, the satellites provide global observations of many other variables that influence climate such as atmospheric temperature and water vapor, snow and ice cover, vegetation, sea and land surface temperature, precipitation and more. These add important information to our records of regional differences in Earth's climate [21].

2.5. Impact of climate change

Climate change is likely to contribute substantially to food insecurity in the future, by increasing food prices, and reducing food production. Food may become more expensive as climate change mitigation efforts increase energy prices. Water required for food production may become more scarce due to increased crop water use and drought. Competition for land may increase as certain areas become climatically unsuitable for production. In addition, extreme weather events, associated with climate change may cause sudden reductions in agricultural productivity, leading to rapid price increases. For example, heat waves in the summer of 2010 led to yield losses in key production areas including: Russia, Ukraine and Kazakhstan, and contributed to a dramatic increase in the price of staple foods. These rising prices forced growing numbers of local people into poverty, providing a sobering demonstration of how the influence of climate change can result in food insecurity [22].

Key impacts of climate change on agriculture:

- ✚ Temperature fluctuations: Rising temperatures can stress crops, reducing their growth potential and impacting harvest times, particularly in regions already experiencing hot climates.
- ✚ Changing precipitation patterns: Irregular rainfall, including more intense downpours and extended droughts, can lead to inconsistent water availability for crops, affecting soil moisture and yield.
- ✚ Extreme weather events: Increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events like floods and heatwaves can cause significant damage to crops and infrastructure, leading to substantial crop losses [23].

- ✚ Pest and disease outbreaks: Warmer temperatures can expand the habitats of pests and diseases, increasing their prevalence and severity on crops, requiring more pesticide usage.
- ✚ Soil degradation: Climate change can exacerbate soil erosion, leading to decreased soil fertility and reduced crop productivity.
- ✚ Water scarcity: Reduced water availability due to changing precipitation patterns and increased evapotranspiration can lead to water scarcity for irrigation, impacting crop yields.
- ✚ Impact on livestock: Heat stress can negatively affect livestock health and productivity, leading to reduced milk production and meat yields [23].

2.6. Causes of Global Climate Change

Climate change occurs as a result of an increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) like CO₂, N₂O and CH₄. Increased GHGs are associated with economic activities particularly as related to energy, industry, transport and pattern of land use (agricultural production and deforestation). Agricultural activities including land use change and forestry (LUCF) account for nearly one-third of global emissions. Emissions from agricultural sector are primarily CH₄ and N₂O making the sector the largest producer of non-CO₂ emissions [24]. While agriculture also generates very large CO₂ fluxes (both to and from the atmosphere via photosynthesis and respiration), these are nearly balanced on existing agricultural lands. Significant carbon releases, however, results from the conversion of forested land and other GHGs emission arising from agricultural activities such as those relating to (upstream) manufacture of equipment, fertilizers and pesticides, and on-farm use of fuels and transportation of agricultural products. Thus, emission from agriculture come from four principal sectors: agricultural soils, livestock and manure management, rice cultivation and burning of agricultural residues and savanna for land clearing [25]. Nitrous oxide (N₂O) is the largest source of GHG emission from agriculture and accounts for 38 percent of the total global share. N₂O is produced naturally in soils through the process of nitrification and denitrification. Agricultural activities may add nitrogen to the soil either directly or indirectly. Direct additions occur through nitrogen fertilizer usage, application of managed livestock manure and sewage sludge, production of nitrogen fixing crops and forages, retention of crop residues and cultivation of soils with high organic matter content. In- direct additions occur

through volatilization and subsequent atmospheric deposition of applied nitrogen as well as through surface run off and leaching of applied nitrogen into ground water and surface water. These processes have potentials to increase N₂O emission and contribute to climate variability. Enteric fermentation or the natural digestive processes in ruminants such as cattle and sheep accounts for the majority of methane production in this category [23]. Reference reported that it is the second largest source of total emission of CH₄ from agriculture with a 34 percent global share. Other domesticated animals such as swine, poultry and horses also emit methane as a by-product of post enteric fermentation (fermentation in the caecum). Furthermore, manure management which includes the handling, storage and treatment of manure accounts for 7 percent of agricultural emission. Methane is produced by the anaerobic breakdown of manure while nitrous oxide results from handling manure aerobically (nitrification) and then anaerobically (denitrification) thus contributing to the global buildup of CH₄ and N₂O.

Flooded rice fields are the third largest source of agricultural emission and contribute about 11 percent of CH₄ which arises from anaerobic decomposition of organic matter [26]. Similarly, the traditional farming practice of setting fire on agricultural lands and other residues which is a regular farming practice among Nigerian farmers contributes greatly to the emission stock of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O and increase climate change problems. The emissions of GHGs from human activities, no doubts, have influence on global climate change. As a result, the question is no longer whether humans are altering the world's climate but where, when and by how much. Thus, it has become obvious that to prevent the onset of catastrophic changes to the earth climate, humans should be aware of the effects of climate change on human, water, animal and crop production [26].

2.7. Effects of Climate Change on Crop Production

Although climate change may result in some benefits such as extended growing season or more moderate temperature in some areas, the overall effects are likely to be harmful. The worldwide redistribution of disease vectors, that is, the animals, insects, microorganisms and plants that transmit diseases which are already upon Rwanda, could increase due to climate change. Currently, many tropical diseases of crops, severe pest attacks and weeds are common and contribute to reduction in yields of crops. Crops that are excellent competitors under stable environmental conditions often cannot survive when their habitat is altered by rapid change.

Instead parasitic species such as weeds, rodents, insects, bacteria and viruses will quickly reproduce and colonize the disturbed environment. The buildups of these organisms have adverse effect on crop yields and food supply [27].

Rwanda is highly vulnerable to climate change with areas of particular concern being water resources, agriculture, health ecosystem and biodiversity, forestry and coastal zones. The long-term effects will include changing rainfall patterns which affect agriculture and reduce crop yields. Reference stated that climate change has potentials to worsen water security, economic growth prospects, shifting temperature, and more challenging hurdles in reaching the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs [28]. Agriculture and food security are at stake as over 95% of Africa's agriculture is rain-fed. Agricultural production, including access to food in many African countries including Nigeria and sub-regions is projected to be severely compromised by climate change. The areas suitable for agriculture, length of growing seasons and yield potentials, particularly along the margins of semi-arid and arid area are expected to decrease. This would adversely affect food security and exacerbate malnutrition in the continent in some countries and yields from rain-fed agriculture could be reduced by up to 50 percent [28].

Furthermore, revealed that climate change and its effects could irreversibly damage the natural resource base on which crop production depends. The organization explained that extreme climate events (flood and drought) are increasing and are likely to adversely affect food crop and forestry production. These scenarios are currently beseeching Nigerian Agriculture (especially food crop cultivation) as cases of food insecurity persists following flood incidences experienced in the country recently. a critical analysis of the consequences of climate change on food crop production reveals that it is less desirable, though there is relationship between crop production and climate change [29].

2.8. Relationship between Crop Production and Climate Change

Crop production activities rely on operations such as clearing, tillage, application of manure/fertilizer, pesticides and use of machines and other equipment. These operations which are necessary to achieve the goal of crop production in order to meet the food needs of Rwandans contribute substantial emission of CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ to the global stock of GHGs that warms

the environment and subsequently lead to climate change. Climate change on the other hand occurs as a result of the concentrations of these emitted gases in the atmosphere which cause alteration in a number of factors that in turn affect the productivity of cultivated crops [30]. This relationship which is self-reinforcing and self-perpetuating is captured in the schema below: Crop production activities are very essential to the survival of farmers and other households in Rwanda Particular in Nyagatare district. Any decision to stop crop production activities of farmers on the basis of the emission of GHGs is suicidal hence, the need to adopt measures that could keep low the emission of these gases in their crop production enterprises [30].

Figure 2. 2: Relationship between Crop Production and Climate Change

2.9. Measure to mitigate impact of climate change on agriculture

Climate change is one of the most pressing global challenges, significantly affecting agricultural systems worldwide. Agriculture, in turn, is a major contributor to greenhouse gas emissions, which exacerbate climate change. However, through a variety of mitigation measures, the agricultural sector can both reduce its own emissions and help counteract some of the broader effects of climate change. Climate change mitigation refers to actions that aim to reduce or prevent the emission of greenhouse gases (GHGs) to limit the extent of global warming and its negative impacts on agricultural production. These actions focus on reducing emissions, improving energy efficiency, and enhancing the sequestration of carbon in agricultural systems [31].

1. Carbon Sequestration

Carbon sequestration refers to the process of capturing and storing carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere, thereby preventing its release into the air and reducing the overall concentration of GHGs in the atmosphere. Agricultural practices that enhance carbon sequestration help mitigate climate change by improving the carbon balance in the soil and vegetation.

- ✦ **Agroforestry:** Agroforestry integrates trees into agricultural landscapes, capturing CO₂ and storing it in both the trees and the soil. Trees can also provide additional benefits, such as reducing soil erosion, improving biodiversity, and enhancing soil fertility.
- ✦ **Cover Cropping:** The practice of growing cover crops such as legumes, grasses, or clover between main crop cycles helps to improve soil organic matter. These crops absorb CO₂ through photosynthesis and then contribute to the carbon pool when they decompose, thus enhancing soil carbon storage [31].
- ✦ **Soil Carbon Storage:** Practices such as conservation tillage, crop rotation, and reduced soil disturbance help maintain or increase the organic matter content of soils, allowing them to function as carbon sinks. Healthy soils also retain more moisture, improving their resilience to droughts.

2. Reducing Emissions from Agriculture

Agriculture contributes significantly to GHG emissions, particularly through methane (CH₄) from livestock digestion, nitrous oxide (N₂O) from fertilizers, and CO₂ from land-use changes. Several mitigation strategies can help reduce emissions across different sectors of agricultural production.

- ✦ **Improved Livestock Management:** Methane emissions from livestock (especially ruminants such as cattle) are a major source of GHGs in agriculture. Mitigation measures include better feed management, dietary supplements to reduce methane production, and optimizing livestock health and productivity. For example, feeding livestock higher-quality forage can reduce the amount of methane produced during digestion [32].
- ✦ **Optimizing Fertilizer Use:** The use of nitrogen-based fertilizers in agriculture is a significant source of nitrous oxide emissions. Optimizing fertilizer use through practices

like precision agriculture (which tailors the application of fertilizers to the specific needs of crops) can reduce excess fertilizer application and the resulting GHG emissions. Techniques like split fertilizer application and the use of slow-release fertilizers can also minimize emissions.

- ✦ **Precision Farming:** Precision farming technologies, such as GPS, sensors, and data analytics, enable farmers to optimize inputs such as water, fertilizers, and energy. By reducing overuse of resources, precision farming reduces the energy and material footprint of farming, while also cutting emissions. These technologies can also help monitor crop health and reduce the use of pesticides and herbicides [33].

3. Renewable Energy Use

The agricultural sector can reduce its reliance on fossil fuels by integrating renewable energy sources into farming practices. Shifting to renewable energy can help reduce the carbon footprint of agricultural operations while providing long-term cost savings.

- ✦ **Solar Energy:** Solar panels can be used on farms to provide energy for irrigation, lighting, and other farm operations. Solar-powered water pumps, for example, are an effective way to reduce the use of diesel or electric-powered pumps, which emit GHGs.
- ✦ **Wind Energy:** Wind turbines can generate electricity for farm operations, such as grain drying, water pumping, and greenhouse ventilation. Wind energy is particularly useful for farms located in areas with consistent wind patterns [34].
- ✦ **Bioenergy:** The use of bioenergy, such as biogas from organic waste or biomass from crop residues, can reduce the need for fossil fuels and provide renewable energy for farm activities. Additionally, using crop residues for bioenergy can prevent the release of methane from decaying organic matter in landfills.

4. Sustainable Land Use Practices

The way land is used in agricultural systems significantly impacts GHG emissions. Sustainable land management practices can help reduce emissions from land conversion, enhance carbon sequestration, and improve the long-term resilience of farming systems.

- ✦ **Reducing Deforestation:** Forests act as carbon sinks, absorbing CO₂ from the atmosphere and storing it in vegetation and soil. Reducing deforestation and promoting sustainable land-use practices can prevent the release of carbon stored in forests and maintain biodiversity [35].
- ✦ **Promoting Reforestation and Afforestation:** Reforestation (replanting trees in areas that were previously forested) and afforestation (planting trees in areas that have not been previously forested) can increase carbon storage, improve soil health, and help restore ecosystems that support agricultural production.
- ✦ **Conserving Wetlands:** Wetlands are vital for carbon storage, water purification, and biodiversity. Protecting wetlands from drainage and degradation can help maintain these essential ecosystem services while sequestering carbon [35].

2.10. Introduction to GIS

A geographic information system is a conceptualized framework that provides the ability to capture and analyze spatial and geographic data, also a geographic information system [GIS] is a system that creates, manages, analyzes, and maps all types of data. GIS connect data to a map, integrating location data (where things are) with all types of descriptive information (where things are like there). This provides a foundation for mapping and analysis that is used in science and almost every industry. GIS helps users understand patterns, relationships, and geographic context. The benefit includes improved communication and efficiency as well as better management and decision making [36].

2.10.1. Components of GIS

Similar to other information technologies, a GIS requires the following components besides geospatial data:

1. **Hardware:** GIS hardware includes computers for data processing, data storage, and input/output; printers and plotters for reports and hard-copy maps; digitizers and scanners for digitization of spatial data; and GPS and mobile devices for fieldwork.
2. **Software:** GIS software, either commercial or open source, includes programs and applications to be executed by a computer for data management, data analysis, data display, and other tasks [37].

3. **People:** GIS professionals define the purpose and objectives for using GIS and interpret and present the results.
4. **Methods:** A successful GIS operates according to a well-designed plan and business rules, which are the models and operating practices unique to each organization
5. **Data:** Possibly the most important component of a GIS is the data. Geographic data and related tabular data can be collected in-house or purchased from a commercial data provider. A GIS will integrate spatial data with other data resources and can even use a DBMS, used by most organizations to organize and maintain their data, to manage spatial data [37].

GIS-Data & Sources: The most important and expensive component of the Geographic Information System is Data which is generally known as fuel for GIS. Acquiring geographic data is an important factor in any geographic information system (GIS) effort. It has been estimated that data acquisition typically consumes 60 to 80 percent of the time and money spent on any given project [38].

Primary Data Capture: Primary data capture is a direct data acquisition methodology that is usually associated with some type of in-the-field effort. In the case of vector data, directly captured data commonly comes from a global positioning system (GPS) or other types of surveying equipment such as a total station. Use of a total station allows field crews to quickly and accurately derive the topography for a particular landscape.

Secondary Data Capture: Secondary data capture is an indirect methodology that utilizes the vast amount of existing geospatial data available in both digital and hard-copy formats. GIS data is combination of graphic and tabular data. Documentation of GIS datasets is known as metadata contains such information as the coordinate system, when the data was created, when it was last updated, who created it and how to contact them and definitions for any of the code attribute data. Perhaps the most important component of a GIS is in the part of data used in GIS [39].

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This section provides description about the project and the strategies to accomplish and achieve the objectives of the project. therefore, it discusses on how the project was organized to reach their both specific and general objects of the study as illustrated in that way of integrated approach for data collection and analysis have been adopted for better understanding of the area, all necessary information and data needed in our project was collected in order to carry out a successful completion of the project goals. it shows the means and collection of data to be used to carry out project properly and successfully, where these methods include description of the study area, data acquisition methods, data processing, limitation and resources. it also carries out the description of the study area, data acquisition and necessary explication on data processing.

3.2: DESRIPTION OF STUDY AREA

Nyagatare District is the second most populous district in Rwanda, located in the Eastern Province. It is situated between approximately 1°18'S - 1°50'S latitude and 30°00'E - 30°45'E longitude and has an elevation ranging from 1,400 m to 1,825 m above sea level. The district covers an area of approximately 1,741 km², making it the most extensive district in Rwanda.

Nyagatare lies in an area of grassy plains, and low hills, with excellent views in all directions, including the mountains of southern Uganda and, The district has a higher temperature compared to the other parts of the country. It also receives lower precipitations. The land is not farmed as extensively as other areas of the country, and there is a large amount of cattle. The area has a higher average daytime temperature than the Rwandan average, and lower precipitation, which come sometimes lead to droughts. The District of Nyagatare is one of the seven districts making the Eastern Province. It is divided into 14 Sectors made of 106 cells and 630 Villages. Spreading an area of 1.741 square kilometers, the district borders with Uganda at the north, Tanzania at its East, at the South by Gatsibo District and by Gicumbi District of the Northern Province on the Western border.

Figure 3. 1: Study area map

3.3. Data Collection

The Secondary data collection method has been obtained from various sources satellite imageries. This type of data collection was used in this research. Satellite data that comprised of two years multi - temporal satellite imageries (LANDSAT 8 and 9 images of 2016-2024) acquired from the USGS. In this study, Landsat images was used in the LULC classification and change detection. The image data files have been downloaded in zipped files from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) website and extracted to Tiff format files. The downloaded images then will be converted to image format in Tiff and the pre-processing procedure.

3.4. Data processing

3.4.1. Image Pre-Processing

Pre-processing aims to correct distorted data in order to create more faithful representation of the original scene, this typically involves the initial processing of raw image data to correct for geometric distortions, to calibrate the data radio-metrically, and to eliminate noise present in the data. Moreover, during the image pre-processing the Layer staking, subset and resolution merge was done with consideration the property in Landsat 8 and 9.

Layer stacking to build a new multiband file from Geo-referenced images of various pixel sizes, extents, and projections. The input bands had been re-sampled and re-projected to a common user-selected output projection and pixel size. The output file usually has a geographic extent that either encompasses all of the input file extents or only the data extent where all of the files overlap. Accordingly, six bands of the Landsat 8 images (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7) of each year and 6 bands (1,2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7) for Landsat 9 were layer stacked to form one full image with all bands to help the interpreter understand all features in the study area. Layer stacking had been done for six bands.

3.4.2. Image processing

1. Image classification

The overall objective of image classification was categorized all pixels of an image into land cover classes. Normally, multispectral data was used to perform the classification, and the spectral pattern present within the data for each pixel was used as numerical basis for categorization. In this study supervised classification was used where the operator determines the areas where a particular type of land cover was present and then the computer computes the spectral signatures. Totally, five LULC classes were established as Agriculture, built up, forest, bare land and water bodies. In the supervised classification technique, the maximum likely hood algorithm was classifying the image based on the training sites (signatures) provided by the user based on the field knowledge. The maximum likelihood classifier was one of the most popular methods of classification in remote sensing, in which a pixel with the maximum likelihood was classified into the corresponding classes. The method was used in this project because it had some advantages in that: The classifier quantitatively evaluates both the variance and covariance of the category spectral response patterns when classifying an unknown pixel. This was done by assuming that the distribution of the cloud

of points forming the category training data was normally distributed. The probability density functions were used to classify an unidentified pixel by computing the probability of the pixel value belonging to each class. Two dated Landsat images (2016 - 2024) were compared using supervised classification technique. After land use/cover classification system has been chosen, training sites were carefully selected in sufficient homogeneity to maximize the accuracy of classification in the image. In the supervised classification technique, three images with different dates were independently classified. This step was probably the most important part of supervised classification, for it's the spectral signatures extracted from these sites that was determine the overall classification accuracy, and thus the utility of the final thematic map. Accurate classifications were imperative to insure precise change-detection results.

2. Accuracy assessment

Accuracy assessment or validation was a critical step in the handling of remote sensing data. The overall accuracy of the classified image compares how each of the pixels is arranged versus the actual land conditions acquired from their corresponding ground truth information. Ground truth points were collected using a Google earth which were used to assess the accuracy of classified image. These points were later used to assess the accuracy of the classified images.

A subset through this tool analyst can get only part of satellite image which covers study area. In this case user can subset image for that part only for further digital image processing. Its mean, this process reduces time and efforts for digital image processing.

Resolution merge different data such as satellite imagery from the same sensor but with different resolution, satellite imagery from different sensors with varying resolution, satellite imagery with ancillary information can be merged to improve the visual and analytical quality of the data. In other words, is combining high-resolution image include panchromatic band of 15m with other bands which has 30m of resolution

3. Change detection

Two dated Landsat images (2016 - 2024) have been compared using supervised classification technique. After land use/cover classification system has been chosen, training sites were carefully selected in sufficient homogeneity to maximize the accuracy of classification in the image. In the supervised classification technique, two images with

different dates are independently classified. Those classified imageries have been taken as input for change detection process by using matrix union; this have been provided retrospective analysis of landscape cover change. As result, this have been used to asses Landscape cover of Nyagatare district.

This process of changing detection, images show how different land use/cover classes changed either in built up area, agriculture, forest, bare land and water bodies this change detection was applied on the study area from 2014 to 2024 statistical outcome was obtained, different procedures were used to obtain the land use land cover. After adding both classified images 2014 and 2024 in the Arc GIS software> raster to polygon of each image was done> dissolve of each image also was done to put all class data together> the intersection of both dissolves was done and the creation of new field (change name and area) in attribute table was done> the geometric calculation of the changed class was calculated> the data were saved as dBase table and were processed in Ms excel > the map showing the change detection was obtained through properties of the intersect > symbology> categories> change name> add all values and the map showing the land

3.5. Flow Chart of Methodology

Figure 3. 2: Methodology flow chart

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results

In this chapter, I discuss about results from land use/land cover (LULC) changes of Nyagatare district from 2016 to 2024. The study considered LULC changes that happened in 8 years from. With the help of Remote Sensing and GIS software, Land use/Land cover (LULC) changes were detected. Multi-temporal remote sensing images (Landsat imagery) were used to generate land use/land cover (LULC) maps. Two satellite images were collected, pre-processed, and classified through supervised Image classification stages in ArcGIS 10.8. where some important classes including water bodies, forest, agriculture, bare land, and built-up area were classified and detected for changes using both Image change workflow.

Post classification image differencing was used to show the landscape cover of Nyagatare district The classified study area was mapped, quantified, analyzed and evaluated. The classified images had five land cover classes such as: water bodies, forest, agriculture, bare land, and built-up area, which were presented in differently. Surfaces with similar spectral properties presented a challenge in the classification process leading to misclassification of some land covers.

4.2. Land use/land cover of the Nyagatare district in 2016

Figure 4.1 describes the different land cover types existing in study area in 2016. The classes type was identified during image classification are five, where yellow color represents the area covered by agriculture, red color represents the built-up Area in the study area, green color represent forest, blue color present area covered by water bodies and orange color represent bare land.

Figure 4. 1: LULC Map of Nyagatare district 2016

Table 4.1 shows the land use land cover (LULC) map of Nyagatare District in 2016 shows five classes, including Water Bodies, Built-up Area, Forest, Bare Land, and Agriculture. In 2016, Agriculture was the dominant land use class in Nyagatare district. This land use land cover map for 2016 indicates that Agriculture class covered 44.52%, built-up Area class covered 21.60%, Forest class covered 19.74%, Bare Land class covered 5.67%, and Water Bodies class covered 8.41% of the total area.

Table 4. 1: Class and percentage of LULC 2016

OBJECTID	GRIDCODE	LULC_2016	AREA (HA)
1	1	Water Bodies	15919.83862
2	2	Forest	31423.55817
3	3	Agriculture	58038.07716
4	4	Built up Area	53272.72452
5	5	Bare Land	33116.6654

Figure 4. 2: Bar chart of LULC 2016

4.3. Land use/land cover of the study area in 2024.

Figure 4.3 below describe the different land cover types existing in Study area in 2024. The classes type was identified during image classification are five, where yellow color represents the area covered by agriculture, green color represents the forest in the study area, orange color represents bare land, blue color present area covered by water bodies and red color represent build-up area.

Figure 4. 3: LULC Map of Nyagatare district 2024

Figure 4. 4: Bar chart of LULC 2024

Table 4. 2: Class and percentage of LULC 2024

OBJECTID	GRIDCODE	LULC_2024	AREA IN (HA)
1	1	Water Bodies	1341.863699
2	2	Agriculture	18606.17567
3	3	Bare Land	68178.91638
4	4	Built up Area	103907.7912
5	5	Forest	11.603751

Table 4.2 shows the land use land cover (LULC) map of Nyagatare District in 2024 shows five classes, including Water Bodies, Agriculture, Bare Land, Built-up Area, and Forest. In 2024, Bare Land was the dominant land use class in Nyagatare District. This land use land cover map for 2024 indicates that Bare Land class covered 29.56%, Built-up Area class covered 42.17%, Agriculture class covered 15.70%, Water Bodies class covered 4.7%, and Forest class covered 8% of the total area.

4.5. Change Detection Map of Nyagatare District 2016-2024

Figure 4.5 The change detection map of Nyagatare District from 2016 to 2024 shows significant land cover changes across five main land use types. The classes were identified during image classification, and each class was associated with a specific color on the map: Dark Green (Agriculture - Forest): This area represents land that transitioned from agriculture to forest between 2016 and 2024. The class "Agriculture - Forest" covers an area of 4,600.93 ha. This indicates an increase in forested areas where agricultural activities were previously dominant. grey (Building - Agriculture): The grey color represents areas where built-up areas have transitioned to agriculture. The class "Built-up Area - Agriculture" covers 0.40 ha. This shows a small transition from urbanized areas back to agricultural use. Light Green (Forest - Wetland): Light green represents land that has shifted from forested areas to wetland zones. The class "Forest - Water Bodies" accounts for 2.81 ha. This represents a minor shift in land use, where forested land has been converted to wetland or water bodies. Red (Vegetation - Vegetation): Red color is used to represent areas where the vegetation type remains unchanged, that is, areas classified as "Forest - Forest," covering just 0.05 ha. This shows the continuation of vegetated areas without significant change. sienna (Wetland Zone - Building): Sienna color represents areas where wetland zones have shifted to built-up areas. The class "Bare Land - Built up Area" covers 33,126.69 ha, showing the significant encroachment of built-up areas into previously bare land or wetland zones.

Figure 4. 5: Change detection map of Nyagatare district 2016-2024

Figure 4. 6: Bar chart change detection 2016 – 2024

Table 4. 3: Classes of change detection from 2016 to 2024

OBJECTID	CHANGE_DETECTION 2016_2024	AREA IN (HA)
1	Water Bodies - Water Bodies	1330.531153
2	Water Bodies - Agriculture	13946.20209
3	Water Bodies - Bare Land	626.186217
4	Water Bodies - Built up Area	18.743613
5	Forest - Water Bodies	2.809109
6	Forest - Agriculture	4600.928414
7	Forest - Bare Land	26653.17263
8	Forest - Built up Area	196.185359
9	Forest - Forest	0.048335
10	Agriculture - Water Bodies	0.022781
11	Agriculture - Agriculture	42.451761
12	Agriculture - Bare Land	40122.19102
13	Agriculture - Built up Area	17947.22866
14	Agriculture - Forest	0.080999
15	Built up Area - Water Bodies	0.022765
16	Built up Area - Agriculture	0.403598

17	Built up Area - Bare Land	732.044522
18	Built up Area - Built up Area	52612.486
19	Built up Area - Forest	0.072397
20	Bare Land - Agriculture	0.089566
21	Bare Land - Bare Land	23.781296
22	Bare Land - Built up Area	33126.68969
23	Bare Land - Forest	11.40202

Table 4.3 From 2016 to 2024, various land cover changes occurred in Nyagatare District.

The Water Bodies - Water Bodies category remained unchanged, covering 1,330.53 ha. However, significant transitions were observed, such as Water Bodies - Agriculture (13,946.20 ha), where agricultural land was converted into water bodies, possibly due to flooding, water management, or wetland expansion. Water Bodies - Bare Land (626.19 ha) and Water Bodies - Built-up Area (18.74 ha) show the conversion of bare land and a small area of water bodies into built-up areas, indicating some urban development. Forested areas experienced major shifts, with Forest - Water Bodies (2.81 ha) reflecting small forested regions transitioning into water bodies, possibly due to flooding or wetlands formation. A substantial portion of Forest - Agriculture (4,600.93 ha) indicates deforestation for farming, while Forest - Bare Land (26,653.17 ha) shows that much forested land became bare, perhaps due to land degradation or clearing for urbanization. Some Forest - Built-up Area (196.19 ha) also indicates urban sprawl into forested zones. There was minimal change in forest preservation, as shown by Forest - Forest (0.05 ha), which indicates minimal natural regeneration. Agricultural land expanded, with Agriculture - Water Bodies (0.02 ha) and Agriculture - Agriculture (42.45 ha) showing slight conversions into water bodies and the continuation of agriculture in the same areas. Agriculture - Bare Land (40,122.19 ha) reflects an increase in farming areas, while Agriculture - Built-up Area (17,947.23 ha) shows agricultural land being replaced by built-up areas. A small portion of Agriculture - Forest (0.08 ha) indicates a minor shift towards forestation. Built-up areas also expanded, with Built-up Area - Water Bodies (0.02 ha) and Built-up Area - Agriculture (0.40 ha) showing small shifts from urban areas to water bodies and agricultural zones. The growth of urban infrastructure is reflected in Built-up Area - Bare Land (732.04 ha) and Built-up Area - Built-up Area (52,612.49 ha), with a significant portion of bare

land being developed into built-up areas. Built-up Area - Forest (0.07 ha) reflects a minimal encroachment into forested zones. Bare land underwent substantial transformations, with Bare Land - Agriculture (0.09 ha), Bare Land - Bare Land (23.78 ha), and Bare Land - Built-up Area (33,126.69 ha) showing small areas of land either remaining unused or converted into agricultural and urban zones. Finally, Bare Land - Forest (11.40 ha) suggests some environmental recovery where bare land reverted to forest, possibly due to natural regeneration.

4.6. Impact of Changing Rainfall Patterns on Agricultural Productivity in Nyagatare District

Climate change is having a clear impact on agriculture in Nyagatare District, especially through long periods of drought. The rainfall data from Mateo Rwanda shows changes in rainfall patterns, with less rain during important farming seasons. These long dry periods, along with unpredictable rainfall, have lowered soil moisture, which harms crop growth and makes water more scarce. As a result, farmers in the area are struggling to keep their farming practices sustainable. This shows the urgent need for solutions to adapt to climate change and protect food security and livelihoods.

Rainfall in Nyagatare affects farming and water supply. The north and central parts get less rain, making drought a big challenge for crops and livestock. Farmers here need irrigation and should plant drought-resistant crops like sorghum and millet. The southern areas receive more rain, helping crops grow but also leading to dry spells during certain seasons. To manage drought, farmers should harvest and store rainwater for use during dry periods. Livestock farmers in dry areas struggle with limited water, so they need to store water and use rotational grazing to keep the grass from running out.

Figure 4. 7: Map showing rainfall of Nyagatare district

As shown on above map, the rainfall distribution in Nyagatare, as shown in the map, varies across different regions of the district. The northern and central parts receive the least rainfall, ranging between 800 mm and 1000 mm annually, represented by light green shades. This indicates semi-arid conditions, which contribute to frequent droughts and water shortages. The southern and southeastern parts experience higher rainfall, ranging from 1200 mm to 1600 mm, with some localized areas exceeding 1600 mm, as indicated by the darker green shades. These regions have relatively better water availability for agriculture and livestock.

Figure 4. 8: Map showing temperature of Nyagatare district

Nyagatare is experiencing the highest temperatures, ranging from 22°C to 24°C, as indicated by the pink and dark orange shades on the map. In contrast, the western part, bordering Uganda, has lower temperatures between 18°C and 20°C, influenced by higher elevation and vegetation cover. These temperature variations significantly impact agriculture and livelihoods in the district. Higher temperatures lead to increased evaporation rates, accelerating soil moisture loss and intensifying drought conditions, making irrigation essential. Livestock farming also faces challenges as heat stress reduces milk production and increases the risk of disease outbreaks, necessitating shaded shelters and improved water management.

4.7. Climate change mitigation measures

Based on the analysis of land use/land cover changes in Nyagatare District from 2016 to 2024, several climate change mitigation measures can be proposed to reduce the impacts of climate change, enhance environmental resilience, and promote sustainable land use practices. These measures are aimed at addressing the observed shifts in land cover, particularly the transition of forests to bare land and agricultural areas, as well as the expansion of built-up areas [40].

1. Promote Reforestation and Afforestation

Reforestation and afforestation are essential to reversing the loss of forested areas and restoring carbon sequestration capacity. The significant conversion of forests into bare land and agricultural zones highlights the need for focused efforts to replant trees in these areas. Restoring forests also supports biodiversity and reduces soil erosion, contributing to ecosystem health. The strategic planting of native trees in large-scale projects can enhance ecological balance and foster biodiversity [41].

2. Sustainable Agricultural Practices

The expansion of agricultural land is a critical factor in land cover change. Promoting sustainable agricultural practices, such as agroforestry and crop rotation, can improve soil health and reduce degradation. These practices not only enhance carbon storage in soils but also contribute to greater food security. Sustainable farming techniques can help reduce the environmental footprint of agriculture, ensuring it becomes more resilient to climate change while maintaining productivity and reducing land use changes.

3. Water Management and Restoration of Wetlands

Water bodies and wetlands play vital roles in water retention, flood control, and ecosystem resilience. The conversion of wetlands into built-up areas or agricultural land has diminished their ability to function effectively. Restoring and protecting these areas ensures the continuation of critical ecosystem services such as water purification, biodiversity support, and flood mitigation. Proper water management practices, including the protection and restoration of wetlands, help mitigate climate change impacts, especially in areas prone to extreme weather events.

4. Urban Green Spaces and Sustainable Development

As urban areas expand, integrating green infrastructure like parks, tree-lined streets, and green roofs becomes increasingly important. These spaces not only reduce the urban heat island effect but also contribute to better air quality and carbon storage. Sustainable urban planning ensures that as urbanization occurs, it does so with a minimal carbon footprint, contributing to overall climate resilience. The development of green spaces also enhances quality of life for urban residents while providing environmental benefits.

5. Soil Erosion Control and Land Rehabilitation

Areas previously covered by forests or agriculture are increasingly at risk of soil erosion, especially in regions where land has been cleared or degraded. Implementing soil conservation measures such as terraces, check dams, and the planting of cover crops is vital to preserving soil fertility and preventing erosion. These efforts help restore degraded land, improve agricultural productivity, and reduce the risk of land degradation, which is exacerbated by climate change [42].

6. Promotion of Climate-Smart Infrastructure

Climate-smart infrastructure involves the construction and renovation of buildings and roads in ways that reduce carbon emissions and improve resilience to climate-related hazards. Encouraging the use of low-carbon building materials, renewable energy sources, and energy-efficient technologies in urban areas can significantly reduce the carbon footprint of new developments. Climate-smart infrastructure helps minimize the environmental impacts of urbanization, promoting a more sustainable built environment [43].

7. Community Awareness and Capacity Building

Building awareness within communities, among policymakers, and within businesses is crucial for promoting climate change mitigation efforts. Educating stakeholders about the importance of sustainable land use, climate change, and mitigation strategies enables them to make informed decisions that benefit both the environment and local livelihoods. Community-driven approaches to land management and climate action empower local populations to take ownership of their environment and contribute to long-term sustainability.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

This study analyzed land use/land cover (LULC) changes in Nyagatare District from 2016 to 2024 using Remote Sensing and GIS techniques. The results indicate significant transformations in land cover over the past eight years, primarily characterized by an expansion of built-up areas and bare land, along with a decline in agricultural and forested areas. In 2016, agriculture was the dominant land use category, covering 44.52% of the total area, whereas by 2024, bare land and built-up areas had become the most prevalent land cover types, covering 29.56% and 42.17%, respectively. The substantial increase in urbanization and the decline in forest cover highlight the impact of human activities on the district's landscape. The change detection analysis revealed notable land cover transitions, such as the conversion of agricultural land into built-up areas (17,947.23 ha), forested areas into bare land (26,653.17 ha), and wetland zones into built-up areas (33,126.69 ha). These changes suggest ongoing urban expansion, land degradation, and deforestation, likely driven by population growth, infrastructural development, and economic activities. While some areas experienced minor afforestation, the overall trend indicates a loss of vegetative cover, which may have long-term environmental implications. The map shows that the eastern and southeastern parts of Nyagatare, bordering Tanzania, experience higher temperatures (22°C to 24°C), while the western part, bordering Uganda, is cooler (18°C to 20°C). These temperature differences affect agriculture, increasing evaporation and making irrigation crucial. Livestock farming also faces challenges due to heat stress, reducing milk production and increasing disease risks. Rainfall distribution varies, with the northern and central regions receiving less (800-1000 mm) and the southern and southeastern regions receiving more (1200-1600 mm). This difference influences water availability for agriculture and livestock.

5.2. Recommendations

To mitigate climate change and its effects in Nyagatare, Rwanda, immediate and proactive measures must be taken by both the government and local populations. Firstly, promoting sustainable agricultural practices is crucial. This includes adopting water-efficient irrigation systems, planting drought-resistant crops, and using organic farming methods to preserve soil health and moisture. Encouraging agroforestry, where trees are planted alongside crops, will help in carbon sequestration and provide shade, reducing the impact of extreme temperatures on agriculture and livestock. Secondly, local communities should be educated on energy conservation and the benefits of clean energy sources. The government should invest in renewable energy projects, such as solar and hydroelectric power, which can reduce the reliance on firewood and charcoal, both of which contribute to deforestation and greenhouse gas emissions. Thirdly, enhancing water management systems is essential to cope with the changing rainfall patterns. Building water storage infrastructures, such as rainwater harvesting systems and small-scale reservoirs, can provide a sustainable water supply during dry spells and reduce the impact of droughts. Additionally, the government should establish early warning systems for extreme weather events and implement reforestation programs to restore degraded land and prevent soil erosion. Public awareness campaigns about climate change, its impacts, and sustainable practices will encourage community participation and a collective effort towards climate action. The observed land use changes, along with rising temperatures and declining rainfall, underscore the need for sustainable land management practices in Nyagatare District. Urban expansion should be guided by proper zoning policies to prevent excessive land degradation and deforestation. Reforestation and afforestation programs should be promoted to mitigate the loss of green cover and help regulate local temperatures. Finally, promoting the use of energy-efficient technologies in industries, homes, and transportation will help reduce the carbon footprint in Nyagatare. By adopting these strategies, Rwanda and Nyagatare can build resilience against climate change while contributing to global efforts in reducing emissions and protecting the environment.

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